

**“The Future of Auditing: Analyzing ISO Auditors'
Likelihood of Short-Term Adoption of Industry 4.0
Technologies**

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ABSTRACT

As the prominence of Cloud, AI, IoT, and Blockchain technologies continues to grow in the era of the fourth industrial revolution (Industry 4.0 or 4IR), their potential impact on various sectors and business activities, including ISO management system audits, becomes increasingly important to explore. This study investigates the likelihood of ISO management system auditors from various countries - including China, Costa Rica, the Dominican Republic, Ireland, Italy, Mexico, Panama, Puerto Rico, South Africa, Spain, Turkey, Ukraine, the United States, and Venezuela - to incorporate Industry 4.0 technologies into their audit processes. The study used a factorial experiment design with the variables cost and difficulty as the main factors while accounting for audit activity as a potential covariate that can influence the likelihood of implementing 4IR technologies. The findings show that the likelihood of implementation is statistically significantly impacted by cost, difficulty, and audit activity. Nevertheless, these factors combined effects were found not significant. The paper also highlights the auditors' worries about data protection and technology dependence, their recommendations for how to incorporate emerging information technologies associated with 4IR, and the need for training and ensuring a standard approach to their deployment.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid evolution of information technology has led to the emergence of Industry 4.0 (4IR), which includes advanced automation, data exchange, and interconnected systems. ISO management system auditors play a critical role in ensuring that organizations conform to the requirements and best practices reflected in ISO MSS standards, thereby helping to improve the organizations' processes. Therefore, implementing Industry 4.0 technologies into the audit process can improve their overall effectiveness and efficiency.

Via a survey of 34 active ISO management system auditors with varying degrees of audits conducted within the past three years, this study explores the likelihood of them adopting Industry 4.0 technologies in their audit processes within the next six months. The auditors surveyed have experience with various standards, such as ISO 9001 - quality management, ISO 14001 - environmental management, ISO 45001 - health and safety management, ISO/IEC 27001-information security management, ISO 37301-compliance management, ISO 37001-anti bribery, and other similar standards.

General Benefits of 4IR

The auditing process can be radically transformed by applying Industry 4.0 technologies, including cloud computing, the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), and blockchain. While IoT devices can enable real-time data gathering and monitoring, cloud

computing offers a scalable and affordable data processing and storage infrastructure. Blockchain technology allows secure and open record-keeping, while AI may be utilized for enhanced data analysis, anomaly detection, and pattern identification. This suite of technologies can be configured to allow auditors to spot risks and patterns that may signal management system non-conformance.

The Goal of the Study

In addition to assessing ISO auditors' intent to adopt 4IR tools in the next six months, this study examines the concerns and suggestions of the auditors, providing valuable insights into the practical implications of integrating these technologies into the audit process. Understanding the auditors' perspectives on adopting Industry 4.0 technologies informs organizations, certification bodies, accreditation bodies, standards bodies, and policymakers in developing strategies to support auditors in embracing Industry 4.0 and helps enhance the overall audit process.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A literature review is an essential part of research because it enables us to learn more about the results of earlier studies and the current level of knowledge in our area of interest. In order to find pertinent terms and themes for the study of ISO auditors' perceptions of Industry 4.0 technologies, a thorough literature analysis was conducted. The keywords included "ISO auditor," "Industry 4.0," "AI," "IoT," "Cloud Technology," "Blockchain," and "auditing." Five specific searches were carried out on the Web of Science, yielding 13 relevant publications after applying the filters for language (English) and relevance to management systems audits. See Figure 1 below:

Figure 1 - Systematic Literature Review Flow Diagram

Literature Review Findings

The literature found that Industry 4.0 technologies are quickly evolving and impacting various sectors, including auditing. Therefore, understanding auditors' perceptions of these technologies' ease of use, cost, and benefits is crucial for their successful implementation (Jagatheesaperumal et al., 2022). Research has explored factors affecting technology adoption, finding perceived usefulness, ease of use, and social influence as key determinants (Murtagh et al., 2012; Pennsylvania State University, 2013; Sercemeli & Kurnaz, 2016).

Auditors see multiple benefits in using Industry 4.0 technologies, such as increased efficiency, better decision-making, and improved audit quality (Abou-El-Sood et al., 2015; Aslan, 2021). Continuous Audit Intelligence as a Service (CAIaaS) provides a framework for intelligent app recommendations, streamlining audit processes (Dai & Vasarhelyi, 2020). However, ease of use is vital, as auditors are more likely to adopt user-friendly technologies (Payne & Curtis, 2017; Sercemeli & Kurnaz, 2016).

The cost of using these technologies is another significant factor. Implementing Industry 4.0 technologies requires financial investment and ongoing expenses for training, maintenance, and upgrades (Bisht et al., 2022; Faitusa, 2019). Auditors must consider potential benefits against costs to determine the practicality of adopting these technologies. Despite current research on auditors' perceptions, a gap remains in understanding how perceptions change with advancing technologies. Further research is needed to grasp auditors' dynamic perceptions and

factors influencing adoption decisions, which can help develop effective strategies for incorporating these technologies into auditing.

This literature review has provided a good foundation for understanding the current state of research on auditors' perceptions of Industry 4.0 technologies and their potential impact on the auditing process, offering more context for the experiment at hand. The review enabled a more profound understanding of auditors' perspectives on adopting these emerging technologies in advance of the inquiry made by the auditors who are part of this study.

EXPERIMENT

The experimental portion of the study aimed to explore the likelihood of ISO management system auditors incorporating Industry 4.0 technologies into their audit processes in the next six months. For this study, Cloud Technology, AI, IoT, and Blockchain were defined and integrated into one term, "4IR Technologies".

The factors were: (a) Cost of Implementation (Hi/Low) and (b) Difficulty in Implementation (Hi/Low). **The response variable was:** Likelihood of Implementation (Hi/Neutral/Low). For this case, the $2^{(2-1)}$ factorial design would involve four experimental runs, with two runs at each level of the factors as shown below:

Factor A	Factor B
-1	-1
-1	1
1	-1
1	1

As shown in Table 2 below, for Run 1, the cost of implementation was set low, and the implementation difficulty was also low. For Run 2, the cost of implementation was set at low, but the difficulty of implementation was set at high. In Run 3, the cost of implementation was set at high while the difficulty of implementation was set at low. For Run 4, both the cost of implementation and the difficulty were set at high.

Table 2 - Experimental Design Matrix Showing Cost and Difficulty Levels for Four Runs

Run	Cost to Implement	Difficulty to Implement
1	Low	Low
2	Low	High
3	High	Low
4	High	High

The data for this experimental design was collected through surveys administered to ISO auditors. Of 40 surveys sent out, there were 34 respondents, thus making for a statistically viable sample.

To match the design, the four questions on the survey were the following:

Table 3 - Survey Questions

#	Experimental Question
1	If the COST of 4IR technologies were LOW and it was EASY to implement them, how likely would you be to incorporate them into the audit process in the next six months? (Hi/Neutral/Low)
2	If the COST of these technologies were LOW, but it was DIFFICULT to implement them, how likely would you be to incorporate them into the audit process? (Hi/Neutral/Low)
3	If the COST of 4IR technologies were HIGH, but it was EASY to implement them, how likely would you be to incorporate them into the audit process in the next six months? (Hi/Neutral/Low)
4	If the COST of 4IR technologies were HIGH, but it was EASY to implement them, how likely would you be to incorporate them into the audit process in the next six months? (Hi/Neutral/Low)

The survey was distributed electronically via google forms, and the resulting dataset was analyzed on Minitab.

ABOUT THE RESPONDENTS

The respondents have diverse backgrounds regarding the standards they work with, reflecting a comprehensive understanding of various aspects of auditing and industry-specific requirements. A considerable number of respondents (18) work with a combination of ISO 9001, ISO 14001, and ISO 45001 standards related to quality management, environmental management, and occupational health and safety management. Several respondents (4) work exclusively with the ISO 9001 standard, which focuses on quality management systems.

Figure - 2 - ISO Standards Audit Experience Among Survey Participants

The above graphic shows that the remaining respondents work with several other standards, such as ISO/IEC 27001, ISO 37301, ISO 37001, HACCP, ISO 22000, and ISO 50001.

These standards cover various disciplines, such as information security, compliance management, anti-bribery, food safety, and energy management.

Professionals working with these diverse standards can offer essential perspectives on applying Industry 4.0 technologies in their respective fields, thereby contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the opportunities and challenges associated with their adoption.

Respondent Audit Activity/Experience

The respondents possess a wide range of audit experience in the past three years, reflecting a mix of industry professionals with varying exposure to different auditing scenarios.

Figure 3 - Audit Experience of Respondents in the Past 3 Years

As can be appreciated in the above graphic, many participants have conducted more than ten audits but less than 30 audits. This implies that they have a good deal of expertise in the area. Some respondents reported performing at least ten audits over the previous three years. This suggests they might need to be more experienced with specific technologies or newer to the auditing field. Then there are some with a wealth of experience who have completed over 30

audits during the last three years. This group can provide insightful information on the immediate effects of incorporating Industry 4.0 technology into the auditing process and the long-term consequences of these developments on the first, second, and third-party auditing of management systems.

Auditor Location / Country

The survey respondents come from various countries, providing a diverse and international perspective on adopting Industry 4.0 technologies in the auditing field. The complete list of countries includes China, Costa Rica, Dominican Republic, Ireland, Mexico, Panama, Puerto Rico, South Africa, Spain, Turkey, Ukraine, the United States, and Venezuela. This wide range of perspectives can lead to a more comprehensive understanding of the opportunities and barriers associated with adopting Industry 4.0 technologies in the auditing profession worldwide.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The results section of this study presents an analysis of quantitative and qualitative data and provides insight into the possible adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies by ISO management system auditors. The quantitative statistical analysis investigates the impact of cost, difficulty, and audit experience on adopting Industry 4.0 technologies. Whereas the qualitative analysis explores the concerns and suggestions of the respondents, providing a deeper understanding of the factors that influence their attitudes toward these emerging technologies. This combination of quantitative and qualitative findings offers a well-rounded perspective on the key factors driving auditors' decision-making processes concerning Industry 4.0 technology adoption in the audit process.

Quantitative Analysis

The study employed Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) as the primary method for the statistical analysis of the results. Using Minitab, this approach allowed for examining the relationships and interactions between cost, difficulty, and audit activity variables and their impact on the likelihood of adopting Industry 4.0 technologies in the auditing process. Below are the detailed ANOVA results yielded by using the General Linear Model option within Minitab:

Figure 4 - Minitab ANOVA - General Linear Model Results

Analysis of Variance					
Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Cost	1	37.303	37.303	33.62	0.000
Difficulty	1	61.122	61.122	55.08	0.000
Audit Activity	2	18.603	9.301	8.38	0.000
Cost*Difficulty	1	2.266	2.266	2.04	0.155
Cost*Audit Activity	2	3.392	1.696	1.53	0.221
Difficulty*Audit Activity	2	2.770	1.385	1.25	0.291
Cost*Difficulty*Audit Activity	2	2.730	1.365	1.23	0.296
Error	124	137.594	1.110		
Total	135	274.934			

Statistical Analysis

1. Main effects:

The main effects represent the individual influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable. This study's main effects are cost, difficulty, and audit activity on the likelihood of auditors adopting Industry 4.0 technologies.

- *Cost:*

The F-value is 33.62, and the P-value is 0.000. Since the P-value is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant effect of cost on the likelihood of implementation.

- *Difficulty:*

The F-value is 55.08, and the P-value is 0.000. Since the P-value is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant effect of difficulty on the likelihood of implementation.

- *Audit Activity:*

The F-value is 8.38, and the P-value is 0.000. Since the P-value is less than 0.05, audit activity has a statistically significant effect on the likelihood of implementation.

2. Interaction effects:

Interaction effects occur when the relationship between two or more independent variables and the dependent variable depends on the level of another variable. In this study, the interaction effects are the combined influences of cost, difficulty, and audit activity on the likelihood of auditors adopting Industry 4.0 technologies.

- *Cost*Difficulty:*

The F-value is 2.04, and the P-value is 0.155. Since the P-value is greater than 0.05, there is no statistically significant interaction effect between cost and difficulty on the likelihood of implementation.

- *Cost*Audit Activity:*

The F-value is 1.53, and the P-value is 0.221. Since the P-value is greater than 0.05, there is no statistically significant interaction effect between cost and audit activity on the likelihood of implementation.

- *Difficulty*Audit Activity:*

The F-value is 1.25, and the P-value is 0.291. Since the P-value is greater than 0.05, there is no statistically significant interaction effect between difficulty and audit activity on the likelihood of implementation.

- *CostDifficultyAudit Activity:*

The F-value is 1.23, and the P-value is 0.296. Since the P-value is greater than 0.05, there is no statistically significant interaction effect between cost, difficulty, and audit activity on the likelihood of implementation.

3. F-values and P-values:

F-values are the test statistics that indicate how much each effect (main or interaction) contributes to the total variability in the dependent variable. At the same time, P-values represent the probability of observing the effect by chance. In this study, F-values and P-values help determine the statistical significance of each main effect and interaction effect on the likelihood of auditors adopting Industry 4.0 technologies. An effect is considered statistically significant if its P-value is less than 0.05.

Discussion of Quantitative Findings

Based on the interpretation of the above statistics, and as is reflected in the table below, the ANOVA results revealed that cost, difficulty, and audit activity have statistically significant effects on the likelihood of implementing Industry 4.0 technologies in the audit process, with p-values less than 0.05.

Table 4 - Significance of the Factors

Factor	F-value	P-value	Significance
Cost	33.62	0.000	Significant effect on the likelihood of implementation
Difficulty	55.08	0.000	Significant effect on the likelihood of implementation
Audit Activity	8.38	0.000	Significant effect on the likelihood of implementation
Cost * Difficulty	2.04	0.155	No significant interaction effect
Cost * Audit Activity	1.53	0.221	No significant interaction effect
Difficulty * Audit Activity	1.25	0.291	No significant interaction effect
Cost * Difficulty * Audit Activity	1.23	0.296	No significant interaction effect

It can be further interpreted that the interaction effects between cost and difficulty, cost and audit activity, difficulty and audit activity, and the three-way interaction between cost, difficulty, and audit activity were not statistically significant, with p-values greater than 0.05. This indicates that cost, difficulty, and audit activity independently impact the likelihood of adopting Industry 4.0 technologies. However, their combined effects do not significantly influence the auditors' decision to incorporate them into their audit processes over the next six months.

Qualitative Analysis of Auditor's Concerns & Recommendations

In addition to the quantitative analysis, this study also qualitatively assessed the survey results to understand better the auditors' concerns and suggestions about adopting Industry 4.0 technologies. This section presents a detailed analysis of the respondents' apprehensions and their recommendations for addressing these issues and facilitating the effective implementation of these cutting-edge technologies in the auditing process."

Respondent Concerns

Analyzing the respondents' concerns revealed several key areas related to the adoption and use of Industry 4.0 technologies in the auditing process. These are summarized in the table below:

Table 5 - Summary of Auditor Concerns Regarding 4IR Technologies

Category	Reported Concerns
Security and Potential Misuse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Safety of personal and sensitive data - Potential for misuse - Cybersecurity and information security issues
Practical Aspects of Implementation and Usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learning curve - Cost and difficulty of implementation - Limitations of industry solutions - Real-time data management - Time required to utilize the technology during an audit
Impact on Quality and Effectiveness of Audit Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not as Effective as In-Person auditing - Over-Reliance on AI-generated content - Compromised Capacity to analyze in-depth situations - Compromised Decision-making due to possible lack of direct, objective evidence

As seen and appreciated above, the respondents highlighted the need for careful consideration and planning when integrating Industry 4.0 technologies into the auditing process. This can help ensure successful adoption and maximize their potential benefits.

Respondent Suggestions

The respondents' suggestions provide valuable insights into successfully integrating Industry 4.0 technologies into auditing. These suggestions are summarized in the table below:

Table 7 - Summary of Auditor Suggestions Regarding 4IR Technologies

Category	Suggestions
Training & Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide accessible online training, - Offer user-friendly manuals explaining technology usage,
Cost & Affordability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintain affordable pricing to enable technology access, - Create cost-effective software
Gradual Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduce technologies gradually, - Evaluate effectiveness regularly
Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement controls to prevent misuse, - Address concerns related to cloud storage
User-friendliness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easy implementation, - User-friendly interfaces

As appreciated above, the respondents' suggestions emphasize the need for careful planning and strategic implementation of Industry 4.0 technologies in auditing. They emphasize user-friendliness, affordability, and gradual implementation, which can help auditors and organizations leverage the potential benefits of these technologies.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the literature review and the quantitative and qualitative analysis of the survey responses, it is clear that the adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies presents a significant opportunity for ISO management system auditors to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of their auditing practices. The factorial experiment revealed that cost, difficulty, and audit activity significantly impact the likelihood of technology adoption. Respondents also expressed concerns about security, practical implementation, and potential impact on audit quality. However, they also offered valuable suggestions, including the importance of gradual introduction, affordability, and user-friendliness.

While the current study provides valuable insights into adopting 4IR technologies such as AI, IoT, Cloud, and Blockchain by ISO management system auditors, much remains to be explored. This research could include respondents from other countries and larger sample size. Also, additional studies can focus on other roles within the management systems of an organization, such as Management Representatives and Top Management. Furthermore, the application of these technologies in other audit disciplines, such as financial auditing, could also be examined.

This study highlights the importance of a well-planned, strategic approach to technology adoption in the auditing field. By considering the concerns and suggestions of ISO management system auditors, organizations can successfully integrate Industry 4.0 technologies and maximize their benefits.

ANNOTATED BIBLIOGRAPHY

No.	Citation	Comments
1	(Abou-El-Sood et al., 2015)	This study investigates auditors' perceptions of the usage and importance of audit information technology. It analyzes the factors influencing the adoption of audit technology and its impact on the auditing process.
2	(Al-Okaily et al., 2022)	This study examines the critical factors influencing the adoption of computer-assisted audit tools and techniques in the post-COVID-19 period from the perspective of internal auditors. It provides insights into the challenges and opportunities for integrating technology into auditing practices during and after the pandemic.
3	(Aslan, 2021)	This chapter explores the evolving competencies of public auditors and the future of public-sector auditing. It discusses the skills and knowledge required for auditors to adapt to the changing landscape o
4	(Bisht et al., 2022)	The article examines the importance of integrating digitalization into firm finances from a technological perspective, discussing the challenges and opportunities of adopting digital technologies in financial management.
5	(Dai & Vasarhelyi, 2020)	This article introduces the concept of Continuous Audit Intelligence as a Service (CAIaaS) and discusses its potential applications in the auditing domain. It also proposes a framework for intelligent app recommendations to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of continuous auditing processes.
6	(Dai et al., 2019)	This article explores the use of blockchain and smart contracts for Audit 4.0, focusing on the accountability audit of air pollution control in China. It discusses the potential benefits and challenges of applying these technologies to the auditing process.

- 7 (Faitusa, 2019) This article discusses the opportunities to improve internal audit in the Latvian public sector. It identifies the factors that can enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of public sector auditing practices in the context of Industry 4.0.
- 8 (Jagatheesaperumal et al., 2022) This article discusses the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and big data in Industry 4.0. It highlights the potential applications, techniques, challenges, and future research directions in this field.
- 9 (Murtagh et al., 2012) This study integrates the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to examine the intention to use e-audit technology. It provides insights into the factors that influence auditors' adoption of e-audit tools and techniques.
- 10 (Payne & Curtis, 2017) This article examines the factors influencing auditors' intentions to train on optional technology. It identifies the determinants that affect their willingness to learn and adopt new technologies in the auditing process.
- 11 (Pennsylvania State University, 2013) This news article highlights a study conducted at Pennsylvania State University that identifies factors influencing individuals' willingness to use new information technology. The findings suggest that perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and social influence are significant factors affecting technology adoption. The article emphasizes the importance of understanding these factors in implementing new technologies.
- 12 (Sercemeli & Kurnaz, 2016) This article investigates the use of information technology products in auditing through the lens of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). It explores the factors that influence auditors' acceptance and adoption of IT products in their auditing practices.

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